

Church of the Panagia and Christ the Savior, Roustika (Rethymnon), Crete

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The twin basilica churches dedicated to the Dormition of the Virgin and the Transfiguration of Christ are located in the center of the village of Roustika in the Rethymnon province. Dated by inscription to 1390-91, only the northern church, the one dedicated to the Panagia retains its paintings in good condition. Each of the two churches has a pointed barrel vault interior and a saddle roof exterior. Two later archways, one in the nave and one in the sanctuary, connect the two churches from the inside. Incorporated at an unknown date, these two internal archways damaged several of the surrounding paintings. Each church is divided into three bays by the addition of two transverse arches. The sanctuary of the Church of the Panagia, divided today by a modern wooden iconostasis, is decorated with a badly damaged image of the Virgin Platytera with an image of the Holy Trinity in the form of the Throne of Mercy in the triumphal arch. Below the Holy Trinity are the Virgin and the Archangel Gabriel forming the Annunciation. The apse is decorated with six co-officiating bishops including St. Nicholas, St. John Chrysostom, St. Basil, St. John Eleëmon (the Almsgiver), and St. Gregory of Nazianzus. The figures along the southern wall are damaged but St. Eleutherius, St. Sophronius of Jerusalem, and the bust of St. Eytychius of Constantinople are preserved along the northern wall. The barrel vault of the sanctuary includes scenes from the Life of Christ including the Ascension, the Anastasis, the Incredulity of Thomas, and the Empty Sepulcher (along the northern half), and Christ appearing to the Apostles, the Raising of Lazarus, and the Entry into Jerusalem (on the southern half). Below these scenes are additional scenes from the Life of the Virgin including the Prayer of St. Anne, the Annunciation to Joachim, and the Meeting of Joachim and Anne. The archways which divide the church into three bays are painted with the Prophets David, Solomon, Jonah and Isaiah on the eastern arch, and St. Barbara, St. Catherine, St. Marina, St. Anastasia, St. Irene, and St. Paraskevi on the western arch. The middle bay of the church holds 24 small scenes divided into a grid pattern on both the northern and southern parts of the vault. These scenes relate to the 24 stanzas of the Akathistos, a hymn dedicated to the Virgin. Each scene is related to the life of the Virgin and the early life of Christ. Below these scenes on the northern wall is the church's dedicatory inscription above a window. The inscription notes that the church was built and decorated through the efforts of Georgios V(la)tas and his wife in the Byzantine year 6899 (1390-91). On either side of the window are the heavily damaged images of St. Photini and St. Leontius. The only standing saints remaining below the southern wall are St. Onouphrius and another unidentified saint. The vault of the western bay includes additional scenes from the Life of Christ including the Betrayal of Judas, the Helkomenos, the Crucifixion, and the Deposition from the Cross. Below these scenes are images from the Last Judgment including an image of Paradise, on the southern wall, and scenes of the Sea and the Land giving up their Dead on the northern wall. The gallery of saints in the western bay includes, on the southern wall, the Archangels Michael and Gabriel, and on the northern wall three military saints on horseback: St. George, St. Theodore Stratelates, and St. Demetrios. The western wall, although heavily damaged, is decorated with some remaining figures from the Apostles Tribunal, a scene from the Last Judgment. To the left of the entrance is the figure of St. Constantine (St. Helena's image has since been destroyed), and on the right are scenes from Hell including some figures of the Damned.

Date Range: 1390 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Roustika (Rethymnon), Crete

Region tags: Crete, Greece

The church is located inside the village of Roustika in the province of Rethymnon on the island of Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See p. 137-141, no. 47.
- Source 2: Lymberopoulou, Angeliki, ed. Hell in the Byzantine World: A History of Art and Religion in Venetian Crete and the Eastern Mediterranean. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020. See no. 68.
- Source 3: Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. IV, 475, no. 4.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: none.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: This is a double church with each church having a pointed barrel vault interior and saddle roof exterior.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Dedicated to both the Panagia and Christ the Savior.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Dedicated to both the Panagia and Christ the Savior.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Other [specify]: According to the dedicatory inscription the church was built and decorated through the efforts of Georgios V(la)tas and his wife.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Stone and plaster.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Reference: Church of the Panagia and Christ the Savior, Roustika (Rethymnon), Crete, Borboudakis, Manolis, Klaus Gallas, and Klaus Wessel. Byzantisches Kreta. Munich: Hirmer Verlag München, 1983. p.261-63